

Sports Media In The Republic Of Iraq, Reality And Hope (Analytical Study)

Ali Abdulhussein Ali

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sports media</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5669150</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this paper is to identify the reality of the Iraqi sports media and try to develop a vision for the aspiration to be achieved to improve the Iraqi sports media. Sports fans and the total sample number was (390) subjects divided into (45) for the exploratory study and (349) for the basic study. The researcher used the questionnaire (prepared by the researcher) as a tool for data collection, the results of the study concluded that there are shortcomings in the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq, there are obstacles in the reality of the capabilities of sports media in Iraq, there are shortcomings in the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq, there are shortcomings in the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq, then the researcher Through the conclusions of the research, we hope to improve the goals, capabilities, responsibilities and duties, and evaluate and follow up the Iraqi sports media.</i></p>

Introduction

Sports media is part of the march of nations, and a long record of sporting achievements and gains for countries and peoples, through participation in sports activities locally and abroad, and it is the bridge through which the public crosses from time to time through sports competitions.

There is no doubt that the media is of great importance in achieving the comprehensive development of the individual and society, in a way that achieves the happiness of the individual and the advancement of society. In fact, building the state economically, socially and politically requires the use of various media, and from here it becomes clear the importance of sports media in carrying out its duty, in addition to increasing its sources and intertwining Sports in other fields. ⁽¹⁾

The media does not affect unless the person has a willingness to do so. The main role of the media is to support the strong and fixed opinions and beliefs of the people, not to change them. ⁽²⁾

There are many types and forms of sports media, and the types of sports media can be classified into readable: it depends on the written word (such as newspapers - books - magazines - flyers - posters). Audio-visual sports: It depends on human hearing and sight (such as (cinema - television - video - the Internet). Fixed sports media: which people go to view it, such as (exhibitions - conferences - theatres).⁽³⁾

The most important principles of sports media are that the media should be suitable for the audience that the media messages depend on honest sources, the selection of the appropriate time for the dissemination of media messages and the mutual influence between the institution and the public. ⁽⁴⁾

One of the conditions that must be met in the appropriate media for the recipient is to avoid lies or to fall into contradictions because lies often satisfy people at the time of their issuance but quickly lead to disappointment when lying or exaggeration is discovered. Lies may include statistical data or price reductions. These are the most dangerous types of media the misleading one it leads to the spread of chaos among the people, so it takes into account that it deals with honest topics so that the public does not get bored or lose hope ⁽⁵⁾

The main objective of any media message is to convey meaning, value or news to the target audience, with the aim of making an impact or spreading innovative ideas that will push society towards growth and development, and the media has a direct and indirect impact on children who are exposed to it, whether Whether the exposure is selective or non-selective, as communication through different means prepares children to participate to some degree in situations or experiences that they may not go through in their normal lives so that it can be said that the media has a role to influence perceptions, motives, trends, levels of understanding, interests, tastes, values, and behavior patterns. Children, regardless of the extent of the impact ⁽⁶⁾.

The objectives of sports media are to spread sports culture by introducing the public to the rules and laws of various sports and games and activities, and the modifications that may occur to them, to establish and preserve sports values, principles and trends, as every society has a value system that shapes and defines patterns of sports behavior in accordance with those values and principles ⁽⁷⁾.

The study of sports media is of great importance as it is one of the most important outcomes of the process of socialization in society, and one of the influential determinants of individual and group behavior. For recreation or public health⁽⁸⁾.

The sports media performs the task of mobilizing the masses, to ensure the support of the national teams and teams, and work to awaken the patriotic sense and the national feeling of the masses, to push them to rally around the team in order to achieve victory, It also provides justifications for the defeat of the national team and its exit from the championships, although these justifications may not be based on a valid basis.⁽⁹⁾.

Despite the technical development witnessed by the sports media, the relationship between it and the sporting event has become governed by the logic of money in an ascending manner, especially with the emergence of competition between television stations, and the emergence of specialized encrypted channels, which depend on the viewer paying a quarterly or annually sum, in exchange for decoding transmission⁽¹⁰⁾.

It is possible that the sports media may also be one of the causes of sports violence, albeit indirectly, or in multiple and intentional forms. Because the main goal of sports media is to spread sports culture, not destroy it, but sports competitions include a huge stock of dramatic scenes and interesting scenarios, representing a basic show for television channels, the audience is demanding more, and major companies are using sports as a marketing tool⁽¹¹⁾.

It is clear from the previous presentation that there is no doubt that we live in the era of globalization and information technology, in the era in which the new media dominated all the interests of individuals. In changing the world of sports dramatically, as it transformed it from mere amateur entertainment competitions to technology and works that focus on the spectator, and the importance of sports media is clear in that it serves as the public school that continues the work of various sports institutions such as clubs and youth centers. The researcher noted that sports media in Iraq It is not at the appropriate level for the value of Iraqi sports, and the achievements it has achieved, so the researcher tried in this study to determine the reality of the Iraqi sports media and try to develop a vision for the hope that is required to be achieved to upgrade the Iraqi sports media.

Research objective:

The study aims to determine the reality of the Iraqi sports media and try to develop a vision for the aspiration to be achieved to improve the Iraqi sports media, by identifying:

- Reality and hope in the objectives of sports media in Iraq.
- Reality and hope in the possibilities of sports media in Iraq.
- Reality and hope in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq.
- Reality and hope in the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq.

Study questions:

- What is the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq and what is hoped to improve it?
- What is the reality of the potential of sports media in Iraq and what the hope for improving it is?
- What is the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq and what is hoped to improve it?
- What is the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq and what is hoped to improve it?

Related studies:

First, Arabic studies:

1. **Hanan Nile's (2018)**⁽¹¹⁾ entitled "Professional Standards for Media Performance in Sports Programs on Egyptian Satellite Channels", the study aims to identify the method of media handling of events and topics presented in sports programs on Egyptian public and private satellite channels, in order to reach results useful in monitoring The reality of these programs and the extent of commitment to professional standards in media performance. The researcher used the descriptive approach. The study sample included 94 episodes with a total number of 163 hours. The most important results were that Nile Sports Channel adhered to the accuracy of media performance by 51.2%, While it adhered to an objective performance rate of 75.1%, As for ON Sport, it has adhered to the accuracy of media performance by 75.4%, While committed to the objectivity of performance by 70.9%.

2. **Mustafa Qamar Al-Dawla's (2020)**⁽¹²⁾ entitled "Assessing the performance of sports media in covering the Men's Handball World Cup 2019", the study aims to identify the role of sports media in covering the Men's Handball World Cup 2019, Through the interest of satellite channels in the importance of the Men's Handball World Cup 2019, The extent of broadcasting the championship matches on satellite channels, or the extent of the spread of the championship through broadcasting its matches on more than one satellite channel at different times. The satellite channels of the Handball World Cup are weak, and the spread of the tournament is weak due to the shortcomings in the media for the tournament.

Secondly, foreign studies:

1. **Weedon G, Wilson B, Yoon L, Lawson S (2018)**⁽¹³⁾ entitled “Where is the (good) sports journalism?” The study aims to identify good sports journalism, the reason for its leadership and the obstacles it faces, The researchers used the descriptive approach and the study sample included (376) articles from eight leading scientific journals characterized by research in sports media.

2. **Hahn’s study (2021)**⁽¹⁴⁾ entitled “The Impact of Statistics on Enjoyment and Credibility in Sports Media.” The study aims to identify the effect of statistics on the perceived enjoyment and credibility of sports consumers, taking into account the level of audiences and the source of the media. The researcher used the descriptive approach. The study sample included (2618) fans, and the most important results were that statistics enhance enjoyment and improve perceived credibility, the source of the media and the development of statistics affect enjoyment and credibility.

Benefit from related studies:

Examining previous research and studies has resulted in the researcher’s statement as follows:

- The researcher understands the limits of the problem in depth.
- Using the appropriate approach to the nature and objectives of the study.
- Determine the study sample.
- Choosing the appropriate data collection tools for the nature of the research.
- Determine the appropriate statistical treatments to reach and analyze the results.
- Looking at the most important Arab and foreign references and making use of them.

Research methodology and field procedures:

Research Methodology:

The researcher used the descriptive approach using the survey method.

Community and sample research:

The study sample was randomly selected from media professionals and experts in the field of sports media, from first-class players from some sports activities, technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams, sports fans, and the total sample number was 390 examinees divided into 45 for the exploratory study and 349 for the basic study.

Table (1) shows the numerical description of the total research sample distributed over the exploratory and basic study

Sample Categories	Research sample		Exploratory study sample		Basic study sample	
	Number	Percentage %	Number	Percentage %	Number	Percentage %
Journalists and sports media experts	64	16.41	10	15.63	54	84.38
First-class players from some sports activities	112	28.72	13	11.61	103	88.39
The technical and administrative bodies of the first division teams	41	10.51	7	17.07	34	82.93
Sports fans	173	44.36	15	8.67	158	91.33
Total	390	100	45	11.54	349	88.46

It is clear from Table (1) regarding the description of the study sample that the total sample amounted to (390) and the pilot study sample (45) with a rate of 11.54%, and the basic study sample (349) with a percentage of 88.46%, out of the total sample of the study.

Study tools:

The researcher used the questionnaire as a data collection tool.

Questionnaire design:

To design the questionnaire, the following steps were taken:

- A reference survey was conducted for similar studies and references related to the subject of the study, such as the study of Nisreen Abdel Salam (2017)⁽¹⁵⁾, David Caldwell Study (2020)⁽¹⁶⁾, and the study of Muhammad Al Jawyish (2020)⁽¹⁷⁾, And the study of Ryan Broussard, Will Heath & Matthew Barnidge (2021)⁽¹⁸⁾.
- Determining the axes of the questionnaire.
- Determine the vocabulary of the phrases that express the axes of the questionnaire.
- Conducting an exploratory study to determine the scientific transactions.

The researcher reached the questionnaire in its final form and it consisted of four axes:

1- The first axis: the reality and the hope in the goals of sports media in Iraq, and it is divided into first: the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq, with 10 phrases, and second: the hope for the goals of sports media in Iraq, with 10 phrases.

2- The second axis: the reality and the hope in the capabilities of sports media In Iraq and it is divided into first: the reality of the capabilities of sports media in Iraq, which contains 10 phrases, and second: the hope for the capabilities of sports media in Iraq, which contains 10 phrases.

3- The third axis: the reality and expectations regarding the responsibilities and duties of the sports media in Iraq. It is divided into first: the reality of the responsibilities and duties of the sports media in Iraq, which contains 10 phrases, and the second: the expectations regarding the responsibilities and duties of the sports media in Iraq, which contains 10 phrases.

4- The fourth axis: the reality and expectations in the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq, and it is divided into first: the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq, and it contains 10 phrases, Second: It is hoped that the sports media in Iraq will be followed up and evaluated, and it contains 10 phrases, thus bringing the total of the phrases to 80.

Exploratory study:

The exploratory study was conducted with the aim of identifying the scientific transactions of the questionnaire, Annex (1) on the number (45), Examined from the research community and outside the main sample, and the results of the survey reached to the validity and reliability of the questionnaire form, where the validity and reliability were calculated as follows:

First: - Honesty: honesty was calculated using the internal consistency validity, which shows the internal consistency validity, the correlation of the degree of each item with the degree of the axis under which it falls, where the values of the reliability coefficient ranged between (0.571 to 0.813), These values are significant at the 0.01 level, Which indicates the validity of the questionnaire statements.

Second: Stability: The questionnaire's stability was verified by Cronbach's alpha coefficient for phrases, dimensions and axes, which ranged for phrases between (0.720 to 0.809), As for the dimensions, the alpha values ranged between (0.792 to 0.831), The value of the alpha for the questionnaire as a whole was (0.866), and the questionnaire's stability was verified by re-application, as the application was on 8/19/2020, And re-application after a period (ten days) on August 29, 2020, and the calculated (T) values ranged between(0.28 to 1.59), These values are not significant at the 0.05 level, The stability coefficient ranged between (0.878 to 0.935), Which confirms that the questionnaire for evaluating the reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq is stable.

Basic study:

The researcher conducted the basic study from 8/9/2020 to 12/11/2020, where during this specific period the researcher distributed a questionnaire form to the study sample through two methods, the first: direct hand-to-hand delivery to colleagues and close associates within the governorate, taking all The second precautionary measures: Delivery through the (WhatsApp) application for those who could not be reached directly as a result of the Corona pandemic and safety measures by social distancing using sending the following link

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfyUNamUSWXUUR4_zedlBVS4KaBRDPB1x862f1fFPCh888k5w/viewform?usp=sf_link

Statistical methods:

The study data was processed using the IBM SPSS Statistics 20 statistical program to obtain the following statistical treatments:

- percentage.
- SMA.
- Pearson's correlation coefficient "t".
- Cronbach's alpha stability coefficient.
- T-test for independent samples.
- Chi-2 test

Presentation and discussion of the results:

First: Presenting the results of the first axis: Reality and hope in the objectives of sports media in Iraq:

Table (2) shows the repetition, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the objectives of sports media in Iraq)No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	standard deviation	Total approval ratio
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	The goals of sports media are consistent with the general goals of Iraqi sports.	27	7.74	70	20.06	252	72.21	*245.27	0.36	17.77	9
2	The goals are commensurate with the financial and human capabilities currently available.	52	14.90	69	19.77	228	65.33	*162.02	0.50	24.79	6
3	Objectives are clear for those working in the sports field	46	13.18	52	14.90	251	71.92	*233.99	0.41	20.63	8
4	There is a plan to bring sports media to international levels.	50	14.33	52	14.90	247	70.77	*220.17	0.44	21.78	7
5	There are scientific and technical committees to set goals for sports media.	68	19.48	49	14.04	232	66.48	*174.06	0.53	26.50	4
6	Sports media aims to spread sports in Iraq.	42	12.03	263	75.36	44	12.61	*277.38	0.99	49.71	2
7	Upgrading the professional level in various games is one of the goals of sports media.	82	23.50	212	60.74	55	15.76	*121.14	1.08	53.87	1
8	Sports media helps form strong teams.	73	20.92	37	10.60	239	68.48	*199.59	0.52	26.22	5
9	Sports media is working to attract businessmen to invest in Iraqi sports.	37	10.60	24	6.88	288	82.52	*380.71	0.28	14.04	10
10	The Iraqi sports media aims to provide scientific measurement methods to evaluate the shortcomings in Iraqi sports.	41	11.75	106	30.37	202	57.88	*112.79	0.54	26.93	3

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99

It is clear from Table (2) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq), There is significant significance in the value of Chi-2 for opinions, where Chi-2 values ranged between (112.79 to 380.71), these values are significant at the 0.05 level, and the total approval rate ranged between (14.04% to 53.87%), and the phrase Upgrading the professional level in different games is one of the goals of sports media, the highest total approval rate, which reached 53.87%, to invest in Iraqi sports with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 14.04%.

Table (3) shows the repetition, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the hope for the objectives of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	Participation of sports workers (athletes - media professionals) in	292	83.67	22	6.30	35	10.03	*398.62	1.74	86.82	4

	setting the goals of sports media in Iraq.										
2	Helping to raise the level of Iraqi teams and teams.	290	83.09	15	4.30	44	12.61	*392.50	1.70	85.24	6
3	Setting the goals of sports media in the light of the available capabilities.	262	75.07	27	7.74	60	17.19	*278.27	1.58	78.94	9
4	Increasing awareness of the importance of sports (exercise - competition - watching).	315	90.26	15	4.30	19	5.44	*508.97	1.85	92.41	1
5	Urging businessmen to enter strongly into the Iraqi sports market.	261	74.79	58	16.62	30	8.60	*273.22	1.66	83.09	7
6	Standing on the sidelines between all Iraqi teams without bias to one of them.	199	57.02	75	21.49	75	21.49	*88.12	1.36	67.77	10
7	Making long and short-term plans to upgrade the Iraqi sports media.	261	74.79	52	14.90	36	10.32	*270.95	1.64	82.23	8
8	Providing moral support to Iraqi players in all games and all competitions.	291	83.38	28	8.02	30	8.60	*393.39	1.75	87.39	3
9	Communication between the different sports sectors and the public.	283	81.09	32	9.17	34	9.74	*358.18	1.71	85.67	5
10	Helping various games to be self-financed.	290	83.09	41	11.75	18	5.16	*391.16	1.78	88.97	2

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is clear from Table (3) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (hopefully in the objectives of sports media in Iraq), the presence of a significant significance in the value of Chi-2 for opinions, where the values of Chi-2 ranged between (88.12 to 508.97), and these values are significant at the 0.05 level, and the total approval rate ranged between (67.77% to 92.41%), and the phrase “increasing awareness of the importance of sports (exercise – competition – watching)” achieved the highest total approval rate, which amounted to 92.41%, then the phrase “help.” The various games depend on self-financing with a total approval rate of 88.97 percent, while the phrase standing on the sidelines among all Iraqi teams without prejudice to any of them came in the last rank with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 67.77%.

Second: Presenting the results of the second axis: Reality and hope in the capabilities of sports media in Iraq

Table (4) shows the repetition, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the possibilities of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	Some journalists in the field of sports media suffer from a lack of experience and competence.	282	80.80	35	10.03	32	9.17	*353.92	1.72	85.82	1

2	The financial capabilities are available in the field of sports media.	20	5.73	35	10.03	294	84.24	*407.97	0.21	10.74	10
3	Assigning some unqualified media professionals to work in leadership positions.	281	80.52	30	8.60	38	10.89	*349.90	1.70	84.81	2
4	Adequate funding is available for holding meetings and seminars that help activate the role of sports media in achieving goals	43	12.32	31	8.88	275	78.80	*325.23	0.34	16.76	7
5	Sufficient funding is available to host some of the famous international and local sports personalities.	21	6.02	45	12.89	283	81.09	*360.64	0.25	12.46	9
6	There is a website to receive complaints and suggestions for sports media.	49	14.04	24	6.88	276	79.08	*331.40	0.35	17.48	6
7	Acquaint the human cadres with all the sports information on the various sports activities.	34	9.74	46	13.18	269	77.08	*301.14	0.33	16.33	8
8	Scientifically and media-qualified human cadres are available to speak in sports.	57	16.33	26	7.45	266	76.22	*292.96	0.40	20.06	4
9	Modern communication methods are not available to obtain information related to the sports field.	277	79.37	38	10.89	34	9.74	*332.91	1.70	84.81	2
10	Databases are available for every sport since its inception until now.	46	13.18	31	8.88	272	77.94	*313.42	0.35	17.62	5

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is clear from Table (4) regarding the frequency, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the possibilities of sports media in Iraq), the presence of a moral significance in the value of Chi-square "Chi-2" for opinions, where the values of Chi-square ranged between (292.96 to 407.97), These values are significant at the 0.05 level, The overall approval rate ranged from (10.74% to 85.82%), The phrase "Some journalists in the field of sports media suffer from a lack of experience and competence" achieved the highest total approval rate, which amounted to 85.82%, Then the phrase assigning some unqualified media professionals to work in leadership positions and the phrase that modern communication methods are not available to obtain information related to the sports field, with a total approval rate of 84.81%, While the phrase "there are financial capabilities in the field of sports media" came in the last rank with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 10.74%.

Table (5) shows the repetition, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the hope for the possibilities of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				

1	Establishing a media committee in each sports institution in Iraq.	285	81.66	32	9.17	32	9.17	*366.81	1.72	86.25	2
2	Providing modern financial capabilities to raise the level of sports media.	301	86.25	28	8.02	20	5.73	*439.98	1.81	90.26	1
3	Objective selection of sports media leaders.	267	76.50	49	14.04	33	9.46	*293.80	1.67	83.52	4
4	Conducting capacity development courses under the supervision of the sports side (within sports federations), as well as the media side.	239	68.48	42	12.03	68	19.48	*196.92	1.49	74.50	3
5	Making periodic bulletins with developments in the training and arbitration of various sports.	225	64.47	68	19.48	56	16.05	*152.88	1.48	74.21	7
6	Provide the appropriate financial support for the sports media to carry out its tasks.	201	57.59	56	16.05	92	26.36	*98.00	1.31	65.62	10
7	Clarity of the organizational structure of sports media.	222	63.61	55	15.76	72	20.63	*145.21	1.43	71.49	8
8	Develop an organizational regulation that defines the relationship between all participants in the Iraqi sports media system.	246	70.49	56	16.05	47	13.47	*217.14	1.57	78.51	6
9	Establishing schedules for what will be broadcast throughout the year.	257	73.64	49	14.04	43	12.32	*255.29	1.61	80.66	5
10	Create a charter of honor for sports media.	224	64.18	47	13.47	78	22.35	*153.60	1.42	70.92	9

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is evident from Table (5) regarding the frequency, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (hopefully in the capabilities of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the Chi-square "Chi-2" for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (98 to 439.98), and these values are significant at the level of 0.05, The overall approval rate ranged from (65.62% to 90.26%), The phrase "providing modern financial capabilities to raise the level of sports media" achieved the highest total approval rate, which amounted to 90.26%, then the phrase establishing a media committee in each sports institution in Iraq, with a total approval rate of 86.25%, while in the last order came the phrase "providing appropriate financial support for sports media to carry out He performed his duties with the lowest overall approval rate, which amounted to 65.62%.

Third: Presenting the results of the third axis: Reality and hope in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq:

Table (6) shows the repetition, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	There is objectivity and honesty in dealing with sports issues.	37	10.60	43	12.32	269	77.08	*300.68	0.34	16.76	6
2	The opinion is separated from the news.	28	8.02	44	12.61	277	79.37	*333.94	0.29	14.33	10
3	It is necessary to verify the authenticity of the news.	45	12.89	63	18.05	241	69.05	*201.79	0.44	21.92	3
4	There is a high moral standard in dealing with topics.	49	14.04	64	18.34	236	67.62	*185.61	0.46	23.21	2
5	Emphasis on standing neutral between the parties to any sports problem.	51	14.61	33	9.46	265	75.93	*286.37	0.39	19.34	5
6	Respects human dignity in dealing with topics.	30	8.60	41	11.75	278	79.66	*337.52	0.29	14.47	8
7	The athletes' private lives are exposed.	271	77.65	25	7.16	53	15.19	*311.82	1.62	81.23	1
8	The use of experts and specialists in the field of sports media in developing the appropriate time maps.	32	9.17	37	10.60	280	80.23	*345.50	0.29	14.47	8
9	Knows the nature and content of the sports media message and its formulation.	45	12.89	49	14.04	255	73.07	*248.00	0.40	19.91	4
10	Know the target audience of sports media.	35	10.03	39	11.17	275	78.80	*324.68	0.31	15.62	7

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is evident from Table (6) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq), the presence of a moral significance in the value of the chi-square "Chi-2" for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (185.61 to 345.50), These values are significant at the 0.05 level, The overall approval rate ranged between (14.33% to 81.23%), The phrase "exposing the private lives of athletes" achieved the highest overall approval rate, which reached 81.23%, Then the statement that there is a high ethical level in dealing with the topics, with a total approval rate of 23.21%, While in the last order came the phrase separating opinion and news with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 14.33%.

Table (7) shows the repetition, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (expected in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	That the sports program be an	302	86.53	27	7.74	20	5.73	*444.69	1.81	90.40	1

	integrated part of the overall work of the sports media organization.										
2	Awareness and knowledge of the psychological readiness of the target audience and the extent to which they accept and be affected by the sports media message.	298	85.39	29	8.31	22	6.30	*425.75	1.79	89.54	2
3	That the sports media program allow the professional growth of the employees of the sports media organization.	278	79.66	22	6.30	49	14.04	*340.13	1.66	82.81	3
4	Reporting sports news without distortion or distortion and stating the truth without evasion or unjustified cover-up.	238	68.19	46	13.18	65	18.62	*192.42	1.50	74.79	9
5	Verifying the truthfulness and authenticity of the news and not publishing false or unconfirmed information or for propaganda purposes.	197	56.45	74	21.20	78	22.35	*83.97	1.34	67.05	10
6	Refrain from providing some parties with information on behalf of another party.	224	64.18	81	23.21	44	12.61	*155.35	1.52	75.79	7
7	Athletes' private lives are a red line that cannot be approached.	248	71.06	52	14.90	49	14.04	*223.57	1.57	78.51	4
8	Training the available human cadres with all modern scientific and media methods that help to understand the concepts and values of sport well.	253	72.49	41	11.75	55	15.76	*241.67	1.57	78.37	5
9	The available human cadres keep pace with the technological development in the field of media and communication so that they can use modern means of communication effectively.	239	68.48	53	15.19	57	16.33	*194.09	1.52	76.07	6
10	Transparency and clarity towards sports issues.	250	71.63	23	6.59	76	21.78	*242.45	1.50	74.93	8

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is clear from Table (7) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (hopefully in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq), the presence of a moral significance in the value of the chi-square "Chi-2 " for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (83.97 to 444.69), These values are significant at the 0.05 level, The overall approval rate ranged from (67.05% to 90.40%), The phrase that the sports program is an integrated part of the overall work of the sports media organization achieved the highest total approval rate, which reached 90.40%, Then the expression of awareness and knowledge of the psychological readiness of the target audience and the extent to which they accept the sports media message and be affected by it, with a total approval rate of 89.54%, While in the last order came the phrase verifying the news's truthfulness and authenticity and not publishing false or unconfirmed information or for propaganda purposes with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 67.05%.

Fourth: Presenting the results of the fourth axis: Reality and hope in the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq

Table (8) shows the repetition, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of sports media follow-up and evaluation in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	There is a follow-up to the sports media programs from officials in the two fields (sports-media).	0	0.00	0	0.00	349	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10
2	The objectives of oversight are not clear to everyone.	264	75.64	53	15.19	32	9.17	*283.05	1.66	83.24	3
3	Favoritism and personal relationships preclude accountability and accountability.	274	78.51	40	11.46	35	10.03	*320.64	1.68	84.24	2
4	Attention to control over the financial aspects, not the technical and administrative aspects.	273	78.22	44	12.61	32	9.17	*317.10	1.69	84.53	1
5	There is no monitoring system.	261	74.79	56	16.05	32	9.17	*272.33	1.66	82.81	4
6	Sports media programs are periodically evaluated	32	9.17	40	11.46	277	79.37	*333.12	0.30	14.90	9
7	Conducting personal interviews with those in charge of sports programs and identifying errors and fixing them.	47	13.47	31	8.88	271	77.65	*309.55	0.36	17.91	8
8	Analyzing records and documents of what is presented in media programmes.	44	12.61	50	14.33	255	73.07	*248.09	0.40	19.77	7
9	Ensuring the continuous improvement and development of the	50	14.33	47	13.47	252	72.21	*237.36	0.42	21.06	6

	media performance presented in sports media programmes.										
10	The public's opinion is periodically surveyed about what is shown in sports media programmes.	66	18.91	40	11.46	243	69.63	*209.78	0.49	24.64	5

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is evident from Table (8) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2 " for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (209.78 to 333.12), These values are significant at the 0.05 level, While there are no differences in the phrase "there is a follow-up to sports media programs" from officials in the two fields (sports - media), the percentage of total approval ranged between (14.90% to 84.53%), While there is no approval rate in the phrase "there is a follow-up to sports media programs" from officials in the two fields (sports - media), The phrase "interest in controlling the financial aspects without the technical and administrative aspects" achieved the highest total approval rate, which amounted to 84.53%, Then the phrase nepotism and personal relationships prevent accountability and accountability, with a total approval rate of 84.24%, On the other hand, the phrase "sports media programs are evaluated periodically" came in the last rank with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 14.90%.

Table (9): shows the repetition, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (hopefully for the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq) No. = 349

No.	Phrases	Yes		To some extent		No		Chi-2	mean	Total approval ratio	arrangement
		Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %	Rep.	Perc. %				
1	Setting regulatory standards (material standards such as the number of working hours - cost standards - revenue standards - performance measurement forms) to evaluate sports media.	275	78.80	35	10.03	39	11.17	*324.68	1.68	83.81	6
2	Periodic evaluation of sports media programmes.	266	76.22	54	15.47	29	8.31	*291.51	1.68	83.95	5
3	Using the content analysis method as a scientific method for evaluating the media performance of these programs.	270	77.36	32	9.17	47	13.47	*305.44	1.64	81.95	10
4	Attention to note the media performance followed.	295	84.53	22	6.30	32	9.17	*412.03	1.75	87.68	1
5	The use of experts in the field of media and sports media to evaluate sports media programs.	273	78.22	36	10.32	40	11.46	*316.54	1.67	83.38	7
6	Holding periodic meetings between officials of Iraqi sports	273	78.22	35	10.03	41	11.75	*316.63	1.66	83.24	8

	and the sports media system										
7	Determining the competencies and responsibilities of each individual in the sports media system so that he can be held accountable.	276	79.08	45	12.89	28	8.02	*329.95	1.71	85.53	4
8	Establishing a mechanism to receive complaints and suggestions for sports media.	273	78.22	64	18.34	12	3.44	*328.10	1.75	87.39	2
9	Monitoring sports media includes administrative, technical and financial aspects.	280	80.23	19	5.44	50	14.33	*349.52	1.66	82.95	9
10	Early detection of errors and negatives and work to avoid them.	285	81.66	31	8.88	33	9.46	*366.83	1.72	86.10	3

Chi-2 significant at the level of 0.05 = 5.99.

It is evident from Table (9) regarding the frequency, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (it is hoped for the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq), the presence of a significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2 " for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (291.51) to 412.03), These values are significant at the 0.05 level, The overall approval rate ranged between (81.95% to 87.68%), The phrase "interesting in observing the media performance followed" achieved the highest total approval rate, which amounted to 87.68%, then the phrase "establishing a mechanism to receive complaints and suggestions for sports media," with a total approval rate of 87.39%, While in the last order came the phrase using the content analysis method as a scientific method to evaluate the media performance of these programs with the lowest total approval rate, which amounted to 81.95%.

Fifth: The significance of the differences between the categories of the research sample the axes and dimensions of the questionnaire:

Table (10) Analysis of the variance between the four sample categories (media professionals and sports media experts - first-class players in some sports activities - technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams - sports fans) in the axes and dimensions of a questionnaire for evaluating reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq

Variables	Contrast source	degrees of freedom	sum squares	of mean squares	F value	Level sig	Type sig
First Axis: Reality and Hope in the Objectives of Sports Media in Iraq	between categories	3	2.69	0.90	0.13	0.94	Non sig
	within categories	345	2345.25	6.80			
	Total	348	2347.94				
	between categories	3	97.85	32.62	*5.03	0.00	sig
	within categories	345	2235.81	6.48			
	Total	348	2333.66				
The second axis: Reality and hope in the	between categories	3	1.90	0.63	0.22	0.88	Non sig
	within	345	976.21	2.83			

possibilities of sports media in Iraq	Iraq	categories						
		Total	348	978.10				
	Second: The hope for the capabilities of sports media in Iraq	between categories	3	10.16	3.39	0.72	0.54	Non sig
		within categories	345	1610.97	4.67			
	Total	348	1621.13					
The third axis: Reality and hope in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq	First: The reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq	between categories	3	5.74	1.91	0.36	0.78	Non sig
		within categories	345	1824.60	5.29			
		Total	348	1830.34				
	Second: What is expected in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq	between categories	3	54.75	18.25	2.36	0.07	Non sig
		within categories	345	2667.98	7.73			
		Total	348	2722.73				
Fourth Axis: Reality and Hope in the Follow-up and Evaluation of Sports Media in Iraq	First: The reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq	between categories	3	3.92	1.31	0.24	0.87	Non sig
		within categories	345	1904.18	5.52			
		Total	348	1908.10				
	Second: The hope for following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq	between categories	3	27.25	9.08	1.61	0.19	Non sig
		within categories	345	1946.51	5.64			
		Total	348	1973.75				

Significant at the 0.05 level = 2.62

It is clear from Table (10) regarding the analysis of the variance between the four categories of the sample (media professionals and sports media experts - first-class players in some sports activities - technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams - sports fans), In the axes and dimensions of a questionnaire for evaluating reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq, there are moral differences between groups in the hoped-for dimension in the objectives of sports media in Iraq, with a value of $f(5.03)$, This value is significant at the 0.05 level, While it is clear that there are no significant differences between the categories in the rest of the dimensions, where the value of P ranged between (0.13 to 2.36), These values are not significant at the 0.05 level, To determine the significance of the differences, the least significant difference (LSD) test was used.

Table (11) The significance of the differences between the four sample categories (media professionals and sports media experts - first-class players in some sports activities - technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams - sports fans) in the axes and dimensions of a questionnaire for evaluating reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq using a test Least significant difference LSD.

Variables	Sample Categories	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Significant differences between the means				
				Journalists and sports media experts	First-class players from some sports activities	The technical and administrative bodies of the first division teams	Sports fans	
The first axis:	Second: The	Journalists	26.02	2.48		*1.43-	0.02	0.73-

Reality and hope in the objectives of sports media in Iraq	hope for the goals of sports media in Iraq	and sports media experts						
		First-class players from some sports activities	27.45	2.44			*1.45	0.69
		The technical and administrative bodies of the first division teams	26.00	3.22				0.75-
		Sports fans	26.75	2.48				

It is clear from Table (11) regarding the significance of the differences between the four categories of the sample, (media professionals and sports media experts - first-class players in some sports activities - technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams - sports fans), In the axes and dimensions of a questionnaire for evaluating reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq, using the LSD test, As for the hoped-for dimension of the goals of sports media in Iraq, the responses of first-class players from some sports activities outperformed sports media professionals and experts, while there are no other moral differences.

Second: Discussing the results:

It is evident from Table (2) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases (the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2 ", opinions, and the total approval rate ranged between (14.04% to 53.87%), These results show that there are problems in the reality of the goals of sports media in Iraq, and these results are consistent with the results of the study of Muhammad Bakri (2020)⁽¹⁹⁾, Bertling (2021)⁽²⁰⁾, Which stressed that the objectives of the sports media are not clear and need to be modified.

The starting point in any successful work is setting goals because they determine the general direction of the collective efforts, and represent a push for each individual in the group to do the work that coordinates the efforts of individuals and units.⁽²¹⁾

Objectives are the attempt to achieve a certain level of progress in a work within a specific time space, and they are an expression of what is required to be achieved.⁽²²⁾

It is clear from Table (3) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (hopefully in the objectives of sports media in Iraq) and the presence of a moral significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2 ", For opinions, as evidenced by these results, the study sample agreed with the suggestions for advancing the goals of sports media in Iraq, and these results are consistent with the results of the study of Muhammad Tariq (2020)⁽²³⁾, and the study of Seid et al. (2020)⁽²⁴⁾.

Objectives are the desired future state that the organization is trying to reach and are important because the organization exists for specific purposes and it is the objectives that limit these purposes.⁽²⁵⁾

Objectives are considered the cornerstone of the planning process. Defining objectives is the basis for drawing up and developing operational plans and programs in order to achieve the objectives.⁽²⁶⁾

It is clear from Table (4) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (the reality of the possibilities of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square "Chi-2", for opinions where the chi-square values ranged between (292.96 to 407.97), These results show that there are obstacles in the reality of the capabilities of sports media in Iraq. These results are consistent with the results of the study of Muhammad Moawad (2020)⁽²⁷⁾, which confirmed the existence of physical and human obstacles facing the sports media.

The potential is one of the components of the sports institution because it works to raise its level if it is used well. Many successful administrations succeed resoundingly despite their limited capabilities, and on the contrary, other departments may fail despite the availability of their capabilities. The proper administration must make an effort to provide appropriate and increasing capabilities.⁽²⁸⁾

The administration makes optimal use of resources, and by that, we mean operating efficiency that is, that the administration obtains the maximum possible benefit from the resources used, and each of these resources achieves the purpose of its use. ⁽²⁹⁾

The capabilities are everything that can contribute to achieving a specific current or future goal, including facilities, stadiums, equipment, budget, climatic and geographic conditions, information and specialized cadres, following the scientific method of planning, management and evaluation to achieve those goals. ⁽³⁰⁾

As shown by Table (5) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (hopefully in the capabilities of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square "Chi-2", for opinions where the chi-square values ranged between (98 to 439.98), These results agree with the results of the study of Mehdi Moradia, Habib Honari, NahidJabaric (2012) ⁽³¹⁾, And the study of Najla Al-Aasar⁽³²⁾, which confirmed her support for the proposals reached by the research regarding the possibilities of sports media.

The capabilities are all the tools, facilities, facilities, buildings, devices and educational aids, as well as the human leaders who manage the facilities and employ those facilities in an effective, safe and attractive manner for individuals within the sports activities program, and their various aspects to achieve the objectives of that program. ⁽³³⁾

Determining the capabilities is a crucial point for planning in the work of the institution because it identifies the resources, supplies and materials necessary to put those tasks and activities into practice, which are the diverse human forces with skill and efficiency, equipment, machinery, raw materials and tools, in order to achieve the goals set before the institution. ⁽³⁴⁾

It is clear from Table (6) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2", for opinions where the chi-square values ranged between (185.61 to 345.50), These results show that the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq is bad, and needs to be modified. These results are consistent with the results of the study of Ahmed Abdel-Fattah (2019) ⁽³⁵⁾, Andrew S. Ross, Damian J. Rivers ⁽³⁶⁾, Which confirmed that the sports media suffers from not carrying out the responsibilities and duties required of it.

The media must abide by some ethical standards in word and deed, which would discipline the people and give confidence and prestige to their leaders by believing their statements and inviting them through the media. ⁽³⁷⁾

Sports media has a manifold role in society that appeared clearly after its wide spread in the twentieth century, so governments took different intellectual policies to allocate newspapers, radio and television channels, and directed them towards their internal goals in terms of raising the level of sports culture for the public and increasing sports awareness for them, and introducing them to the importance of the role of sports in their public and private lives ⁽³⁸⁾

It is evident from Table (7) regarding the frequency, percentage and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (hopefully in the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2", For opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (83.97 to 444.69), and this shows the agreement of the study sample on the suggestions of responsibilities and duties related to the Iraqi sports media, and these results are consistent with the results of the study of Roy (2011) ⁽³⁹⁾, And a study on Ayman (2019) ⁽⁴⁰⁾.

Media planning is "directing the systems and means of communication in societies through a central apparatus to achieve the basic goals of states, especially supporting national unity and accelerating and supporting economic and social development by using technical and scientific methods of communication according to the circumstances of each country." ⁽⁴¹⁾

The impact of the sports media message varies according to its future, as young people are affected more than adults and adolescents more than adults, and the length of an individual's experience and its capacity greatly affects the way he deals with sports information provided by the sports media message, so we find that adolescents are the most affected groups by the media. ⁽⁴²⁾

The influence of the media on the public has become a huge field, but in itself, it has theories, including the theory of direct or short-term impact: This theory is because the relationship of the individual with the content of the media materials of the media is a direct traditional relationship. The individual was exposed to it, whether newspaper, radio or television. ⁽⁴³⁾

It is clear from Table (8) regarding the frequency, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq) that there is a significant significance in the value of the chi-square " Chi-2", for opinions, where the values of the chi-square ranged between (209.78 to 333.12), and these values are significant at the 0.05 level, These results show the lack of follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq, and these results agree with the results of McCarthy's study (2013) ⁽⁴⁴⁾, the study of Mustafa Abdel Salam (2019) ⁽⁴⁵⁾, Which confirmed the lack of follow-up and evaluation of sports media.

It is necessary to follow the plan at certain intervals and make sure that it is going in the direction set for it, and then comes the role of evaluating the plan after the end of work with it, to see if it has achieved its goal and what are the difficulties it faced, as this information is used in planning for the next period ⁽⁴⁶⁾

In addition, performance appraisal is more than just a control process. It is related to human relations and the work environment, as it provides management with a basis to ensure that every individual works with justice and without which the performance reward is subject to randomness, i.e. an administrative process whose effectiveness cannot be proven without examination and evaluation processes. ⁽⁴⁷⁾

It is evident from Table (9) regarding the frequency, percentage, and statistical significance of the responses of the total research sample to the phrases, (it is hoped for the follow-up and evaluation of sports media in Iraq), The presence of significant significance in the value of the chi-square "Chi-2", For opinions, and these results confirm the agreement of the study sample on the suggestions for what is hoped for in the follow-up and evaluation of sports media, and these results agree with the results of the study of Smith, Evens and Osifidis. Smith P, Evens T, Iosifidis P (2016) ⁽⁴⁸⁾, and the study of Islam Abdel Kafi (2019) ⁽⁴⁹⁾.

The absence of an effective and fair performance appraisal system affects the building of the work team. The pursuit of success needs to determine the arrival station. Determining the level of achievement is a very important process, and this requires that there be agreement among the team members on the appropriate method for them. ⁽⁵⁰⁾

A standard must be set for the performance of various work based on the specific objectives. Determining the standard is a treasure for the organization's awareness, through which it is possible to evaluate performance and differentiate between the performances of employees, and therefore each individual seeks to reach the required performance standards, which is reflected in the results. ⁽⁵¹⁾

It is evident from Table (10) and Table (11) regarding the analysis of the variance between the four sample categories (media professionals and sports media experts - first-class players in some sports activities - technical and administrative bodies for first-class teams - sports fans), In the axes and dimensions of a questionnaire for assessing reality and expectations in sports media in Iraq, and the presence of moral differences between groups in the hoped-for dimension in the objectives of sports media in Iraq, while it is clear that there are no moral differences between groups in the rest of the dimensions and for the hoped-for dimension in the objectives of sports media in Iraq, the responses outperformed First-class players from some sports activities include media professionals and sports media experts, while there are no other moral differences.

The researcher attributes these differences to the lack of clarity in the objectives of the sports media, as well as to the failure of the sports media to perform its duties and responsibilities, due to the weak capabilities of the media and the absence of a monitoring and follow-up system. Antonovic (2018) ⁽⁵²⁾.

One of the most important principles of sports media is that the media message is characterized by honesty and clarity, reliance on the human element and the need for continuous evaluation of media messages. ⁽⁵³⁾

Among the factors affecting sports media are the interim evaluation of the media program and the study of the various media or propaganda influences, communication channels and means, and environmental variables (political - economic - social - educational - cultural). ⁽⁵⁴⁾

As one of the characteristics that must be available in a successful media message, is that it be meaningful in the life of the recipient and the meaning of being meaningful is that it is related to the life of the audience, expressive of it, useful and influential in its behavior and trends, and that it is able to gain the trust of the recipient in the sense that it is free from Exaggeration in its preparation and exaggeration in the way it is presented, for the media message preparer to benefit from the prevailing opinions and trends. ⁽⁵⁵⁾

Conclusions and Recommendations:

Conclusions:

In light of the objectives and procedures of the study, the researcher reached the following conclusions:

1. There are shortcomings in the reality of the objectives of sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - It is not one of the goals of the Iraqi sports media to raise the professional level in the various games.
 - Sports media does not aim to spread sports in Iraq.
 - The Iraqi sports media does not aim to provide scientific measurement methods to evaluate the shortcomings in Iraqi sports.
2. The hope for the goals of sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - Increasing awareness of the importance of sports (exercise - competition - watching).
 - Helping various games to be self-financed.
 - Providing moral support to Iraqi players in all games and all competitions.

3. There are obstacles in the reality of the capabilities of sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - Some media professionals in the field of sports media suffer from a lack of experience and competence.
 - Assigning some unqualified media professionals to work in leadership positions.
 - Modern methods of communication are not available, as in the developed world, to obtain information related to the sports field.
4. It is hoped for the potentials of sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - Providing modern financial capabilities to raise the level of sports media.
 - Establishing a media committee in each sports institution in Iraq.
 - Conducting capacity development courses under the supervision of the sports side (within sports federations), as well as the media side.
5. There are shortcomings in the reality of the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - The athletes' private lives are exposed.
 - There is no high moral standard in dealing with topics.
 - It does not take into account the verification of the truth of the news.
6. It is hoped that the responsibilities and duties of sports media in Iraq are the most important:
 - That the sports program be an integrated part of the overall work of the sports media organization.
 - Awareness and knowledge of the psychological readiness of the target audience and the extent to which it accepts the sports media message and is affected by it.
 - That the sports media program allow the professional growth of the employees of the sports media organization.
7. There are shortcomings in the reality of following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - Paying attention to controlling the financial aspects, not the technical and administrative aspects.
 - Favoritism and personal relationships prevent accountability and accountability.
 - The objectives of oversight are not clear to everyone.
8. It is hoped for following up and evaluating sports media in Iraq, the most important of which are:
 - Paying attention to the media performance followed.
 - Establishing a mechanism to receive complaints and suggestions for sports media.
 - Early detection of errors, negatives, and work to avoid them.

Recommendations:

Unser the study conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

- The participation of workers in the sports field (athletes - media professionals), in setting the objectives of sports media in Iraq.
- Communication between the different sports sectors and the public.
- That one of the objectives of the sports media is to help raise the level of the Iraqi teams and teams.
- Urging businesspersons to enter strongly into the Iraqi sports market.
- Develop an organizational regulation that defines the relationship between all participants in the Iraqi sports media system.
- Make periodic bulletins of developments in the training and arbitration of various sports.
- Work on the clarity of the organizational structure of the sports media.
- Keeping pace with the available human cadres of technological development in the field of media and modern communication so that they can use modern means of communication effectively.
- Refraining from providing some parties with information on behalf of another party.
- Periodic evaluation of sports media programmers.
- Determining the terms of reference and responsibilities of each individual in the sports media system so that he can be held accountable.
- The use of experts in the field of media and sports media to evaluate sports media programs.
- Setting control standards (material standards such as the number of working hours - cost standards - revenue standards - performance measurement forms) to evaluate sports media.

References

Ibrahim Abdel Hadi.(2000). Management Concepts, Types and Operations, University Knowledge House,

- Alexandria.
- Ibrahim Abdel-Maqsood and Hassan El-Shafei.(2004). The Scientific Encyclopedia of Sports Management, Planning in the Sports Field, Prepared by Dar Al-Wafa We have Printing and Publishing, Alexandria.
- Ibrahim Muhammad. (1994).The Origins of Modern Media and Its Applications, Al-Safa Press, Makkah Al-Mukarramah.
- Abu Al-Naga Ezz Al-Din.(2004). Sports potential and its role in achieving the goals of physical education, Mansoura University Press for Printing and Publishing, Mansoura.
- Ahmed Abdel-Fattah.(2019). Analytical study of the role of sports media and its impact on public opinion, unpublished MA thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Helwan University.
- Islam Abdel Kafi.(2019). A proposed model for activating the role of the media industry in the Egyptian sports channels, an unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education, Minya University.
- Amin Al-Khouli and Jamal Al-Shafei. (2000).The Curriculum of Contemporary Physical Education, Dar Al-Fikr Al-Arabi, Cairo.
- Bashir Abbas, Abdullah Barakat.(2001). Principles of Management Science, Al-Raed Scientific Library, Alexandria.
- Hossam El-Din El-Sayed.(2003). The role of mass media in spreading sports culture among students of some Egyptian universities, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education, Tanta University.
- Hassan El-Shafei.(2003). Media in Physical Education and Sports, Dar Al-Wafa Ladonia Printing and Publishing, Alexandria.
- Hamid Al-Jalimi.(1998). Media Planning, Concepts and General Framework, Dar Al-Shorouk.
- Hanan Nile. (2018). Professional standards for media performance in sports programs on Egyptian satellite channels, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Mass Communication, Cairo University.
- Khalifa Behbehani.(2004). Encyclopedia of Management in Sports Organizations, prepared by Faisal Press, Kuwait.
- Khair Al-Din Owais and Atta Hassan. (1998) Sports Media, Dar Al-Kitab Publishing, Cairo R.
- Samir Abdel Hamid. (1999) Management of Mathematical Bodies, Modern Theories and Their Applications, Manshaat Al Maaref, Alexandria.
- Sayed Mahmoud, Ismail El-Khouly.(1994). Total Quality Management and ISO 9000, BMIC Center for Professional Management Experience, Cairo.
- Abdel Majeed Shoukry. (1995).Media Communication, Development, Future Prospects and Challenges for a New Century, Al-Arabi Publishing, Cairo.
- Abdel Nasser Fathallah. (2000). Arab Television and Sports - Controlling the Relationship, Journal of Arab States Broadcasting, Tunis, No. 42.
- Ali Imbabi. (2007) Readable Educational Media in the Educational Institution, Science and Faith for Publishing and Distribution.
- Ali Ayman. (2019). Sports newspapers' treatment of ultras issues and their relationship to adolescents' attitudes towards them, unpublished MA thesis, Faculty of Graduate Studies for Childhood, Ain Shams University.
- Alia Shukri. (1997). Some features of socio-cultural change in the Arab world, a field study of the culture of some local communities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Dar Al-Jeel for printing, Cairo.
- Omar El-Shahat. 2018).The Role of Sports Media in the Regions in Achieving the Goals of Football in Egypt, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Zagazig University.
- Kamal Darwish, Sobhi Hassanein. (2004). Encyclopedia of Sport Management Trends at the Beginning of the New Century, Volume Two, Prepared by Arab Thought House.
- Muhammad Al-Jawish. (2020). The role of technical progress in sports media and its reflection on the national rich in the Arab Republic of Egypt, unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Helwan University.
- Muhammad Bakri. (2020). The role of electronic media in shaping the mental image of sports clubs in the Arab Republic of Egypt, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Benha University.
- Mohamed Abdel-Ghani. (1996). Total Quality Management Skills in Training, Performance and Development Center, Cairo.
- Mohamed Tarek. (2020).The role of the media and social communication in guiding the youth to practice swimming in some clubs in the Arab Republic of Egypt, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Benha University.
- Mohamed Abdel Aziz. (2005). An objective look at the phenomenon of sports stadium riots, published article, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Alexandria University.
- Mohamed Moawad. (2020). Sports media and its impact on the general trends of the masses, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education, Helwan University.
- Mufti Hammad. (1999).Applications of Sports Management, Al-Kitab Center forPublishing, Cairo.
- Mustafa Abdel Salam. (2019). Trends in modern media discourse towards sports issues, unpublished master's

- thesis, Faculty of Mass Communication, Cairo University.
- Mostafa Qamar Al-Dawla. (2020).Evaluating the performance of the sports media in covering the Men's Handball World Cup 2019, unpublished master's thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Boys, Benha University.
- Naglaa Al-Aasar. (2019). Directing sports media to develop some educational values using kinetic drama for late childhood, unpublished Ph.D. thesis, Faculty of Physical Education for Girls, Zagazig University.
- Nisreen Abdel Salam. (2017).The Role of Sports Media in Forming the Sports Culture of Sadat City University Students, Unpublished Master's Thesis, College of Physical Education, Sadat University.
- Yassin Fadl. (2011). Sports Media, Osama House for Publishing and Distribution, Amman,.
- Andrew S. Ross, Damian J. Rivers . (2020).Sport in the new media landscape: Community, participation and discourse, *Discourse, Context & Media* , Volume 35.
- Cham.Antunovic D., Whiteside . (2018).Sports Media Studies: State of the Field. In: Harp D., Loke J., Bachmann I. (eds) *Feminist Approaches to Media Theory and Research. Comparative Feminist Studies*. Palgrave Macmillan,
- Baskin, Dan Lattimore, Suzette Heiman, Elizabeth Toth . (2001). *public relation the profession and the practice* boston MC Graw Hil.
- Bertling .(2021). *Media Strategies in the Sports Media Sector*. In: Walzel S., Römisch V. (eds) *Managing Sports Teams. Management for Professionals*. Springer, Cham.
- Bind man, Stephen. (2000).The role of the media in sport, sport in prespective, I.S.S.P.
- David Caldwell. (2020). Sounds of the game: An interpersonal discourse analysis of ‘on field’ language in sports media, *Discourse, Context & Media* , Volume 33, March.
- Hahn.(2021). The Effect of Statistics on Enjoyment and Perceived Credibility in Sports Media. *Communication & Sport*.
- McCarthy B.(2013). Consuming sports media, producing sports media: An analysis of two fan sports blogospheres. *International Review for the Sociology of Sport*.,48(4):421-434.
- Mehdi Moradia ,Habib Honari,Nahid Jabaric. The Association Between Informing, Social Participation, Educational, and Culture Making Roles of Sport Media with Development Of Championship Sport, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* , Volume 46, 2012, Pages 5356-5360.
- Richard L. Daft.(2001). *Understanding management*, Harcourt College publishers, third edition, USA.
- Rowe . Sports media. (2011). beyond broadcasting, beyond sports, beyond societies? In A. C. Billings (Ed.), *Sports Media: Transformation, Integration, Consumption* (pp. 94-113).
- Ryan Broussard, Will Heath & Matthew Barnidge. (2021). Incidental exposure to political content in sports media: antecedents and effects on political discussion and participation, *The Communication Review*, 24:1, 1-21.
- Smith P, Evens T, Iosifidis P. (2016). The next big match: Convergence, competition and sports media rights. *European Journal of Communication*.,31(5):536-550.
- Weedon G, Wilson B, Yoon L, Lawson S.(2018). Where’s all the ‘good’ sports journalism? Sports media research, the sociology of sport, and the question of quality sports reporting. *International Review for the Sociology of Sport*,53(6):639-667.

Author Information

Lecturer Dr. Ali Abdulhussein Ali

General Directorate of Education in Wasit / Ministry
of Education, Iraq
